

Medicaid Service Utilization by Beneficiaries with Rare Diseases

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ABSTRACT

This national analysis examines Medicaid enrollees with diagnosed rare diseases (RDs) using 2020–2023 Transformed Medicaid Statistical Information System (T-MSIS) claims data, with primary emphasis on 2023 population characteristics, service utilization, eligibility pathways, and geographic distribution. The study identified more than 6 million Medicaid beneficiaries with an RD, including substantial proportions of children, young adults, and rural residents. Compared with other Medicaid enrollees, beneficiaries with RDs had markedly higher use of inpatient, emergency department, long-term care, outpatient, primary care, and prescription drug services. Nearly one-third were dually eligible for Medicare and Medicaid, and 44.7% qualified through home- and community-based services (HCBS) waivers, underscoring the importance of these pathways for access to care. These findings highlight Medicaid’s central role in financing and delivering care for people with rare diseases and establish an important baseline for evaluating future policy changes affecting benefits, eligibility, rural access, and long-term services and supports.

Introduction

The United States (US) Medicaid program occupies a critically important place in the US health care ecosystem, offering critical medical coverage and long-term care (LTC) to individuals who are aged, blind, disabled, and those in other qualifying categories including eligible children, pregnant women, and certain low-income individuals. Each year, Medicaid pays for about half of all births in the US and about a quarter of all LTC. In 2025, 77 million Americans were enrolled in Medicaid.¹

Although Medicaid’s overall role in US health care financing and the characteristics of its enrolled population are well documented, condition-specific analyses have focused on common causes of morbidity and mortality. Existing studies of rare diseases (RDs)

covered by Medicaid primarily examine utilization and spending related to drugs and biologics, or focus on a limited number of specific conditions. A 2019 study of 379 RDs showed that commercial insurers covered the largest share of direct medical costs, but its adult-heavy population probably underestimated Medicaid's role.² No comprehensive evidence is available to map the geographic variation in overall rare disease prevalence, payer mix, or health care utilization.

The enactment of the Budget Reconciliation Act, P.L. 119-21 (OBBBA), is expected to affect Medicaid benefits, financing, eligibility, waiver authorities, and more, heightening the need to establish baseline data on what to measure if certain beneficiary groups or benefits are adversely affected as the law is implemented.³

This analysis of a national dataset of Medicaid claims provides insights into the characteristics of Medicaid enrollees who have a RD, the services they utilize, and where they access care. This is the first public analysis to identify and group Medicaid beneficiaries affected by RDs. It also contributes new understanding to the health research and policy fields.

Specifically, this analysis examines four key domains:

- Utilization of Medicaid services in individuals with a RD versus enrollees without
- Program eligibility pathways to determine the extent to Medicaid enrollees with a RD rely on home and community-based services (HCBS) pathways forecasted to be affected by recent policy changes
- Age and demographic profiles
- Geographic distribution

Because Medicaid program eligibility varies according to each state's program requirements, the Medicaid claims data also include geographic location (residence). Specifically, our analysis examined where Medicaid beneficiaries with a RD were located by state.⁴

Because the delivery and experience of care may vary significantly across urban, suburban, and rural settings, health care researchers and policymakers have had a long-standing interest in understanding the challenges to access to care and treatment for Medicaid beneficiaries in each geographic context. OBBBA focuses heavily on the impact on rural health care access.

An improved understanding of the RD population with Medicaid coverage is critical toward identifying care gaps, establishing baselines to assess the impact of policy changes, and informing public health priorities.

Methodology

Data Source

This study utilized Medicaid claims datasets from the Transformed Medicaid Statistical Information System (T-MSIS), operated by the Centers for Medicare & Medicaid Services (CMS). Medicaid claims are collected by states and reported to CMS, along with demographic and enrollment data for members. Because each state is responsible

for submitting such data, data quality varies. We included claims data from 2020 to 2023.⁵

Defining, Identifying, and Enumerating the Population

In the US, a RD is defined as a condition that affects fewer than 200,000 people.⁶ At present, more than 10,000 RDs have been identified.⁷ We used a crosswalk of RDs compiled by physician scientists at the National Center for Advancing Translational Sciences (NCATS) rare disease division.⁸ The NCATS file mapped Medical Language System RD biomedical concepts to an International Classification of Diseases, 10th Edition (ICD-10), code that represents a RD (eTable 1 in Supplement).

Once the list of RD-associated ICD-10 codes was established, we linked the RD ICD-10 diagnosis code reported on a beneficiary claim. We included claims from outpatient, inpatient, and LTC setting source files. We linked 1,680 distinct ICD-10 codes to a RD concept. Beneficiaries are included in the population if a RD diagnosis code appeared in the primary position (i.e., that the RD diagnosis was the primary reason for the Medicaid service rendered).

Medicaid Coverage and Dual Eligibility

Some Medicaid enrollees are dually eligible for Medicare. In general, such dual-eligible beneficiaries (duals) receive both Medicare and Medicaid benefits by virtue of their age or disability and income. For dual-eligibles, Medicare is the primary payer for acute and post-acute care services covered by that program. Medicaid provides varying levels of assistance with Medicare premiums and cost sharing, and for many beneficiaries, covers services not included in the Medicare benefit, such as LTC (also known as long-term services and supports in Medicaid). Full-benefit, dual-eligible beneficiaries receive the full range of Medicaid benefits offered in each state.

Home and Community-Based Services

HCBS allow Medicaid enrollees with significant physical and cognitive limitations to live in their home, or in home-like settings, and remain in the community. HCBS encompass a breadth of services, including personal care services provided in a home or residential care setting, supported employment, non-medical transportation, and home-delivered meals.

HCBS are optional benefits for states to provide, and states vary in how they organize their HCBS programs. While some states provide certain HCBS in the state plan, many states use waiver authorities such as Section 1915(c) HCBS waiver authority, which gives states flexibility to cap the number of people who receive services, target specific populations, or limit availability to certain parts of the state. We examined these specific waiver types, as they are reported in the enrollment files within the T-MSIS Analytic Files (TAF).

Rare Disease Geographic and Demographic Stratification

The stratification of the RD population counts, by demographic category, geography, and eligibility designations, only included individuals enrolled in Medicaid in 2023. For purposes of this analysis, we focused on 2023 data; earlier Medicaid enrollment data

was inflated due to the maintenance of effort requirements in federal law that expired with the formal end of the COVID-19 Public Health Emergency in May 2023.

Our analysis examines what is known regarding the prevalence of Medicaid beneficiaries with RDs in rural and semi-rural settings. We used population density as a proxy measure of rurality. To assess the prevalence of Medicaid beneficiaries with RD and non-Medicaid beneficiaries across rural settings, we cross-referenced our data with publicly available data from the Congressional District Health Dashboard (CDHD) project at the Department of Population Health at New York University (NYU) Grossman School of Medicine.^{9, 10}

There were multiple advantages to using these data. First, the CDHD project calculated a District Density Index for the 2022 (118th Congress) congressional districts, which included a categorization of population density and rurality. The CDHD categorized all congressional districts based on household density. Second, these data are publicly available. Third, while governmental data (such as data from the US Census Bureau) would have been ideal, the timeframe of this 2022 data closely matched the 2023 period.

Analysis of Health Care Service Utilization

Across the categories of service utilization, we separately analyzed beneficiaries with chronic and acute RDs because their respective utilization patterns may be impacted by the length of their disease. We used the US Department of Health and Human Services (HHS) Healthcare Cost and Utilization Project (HCUP) documentation to implement an algorithm to classify a given RD.¹¹ We classified diseases as “chronic” if they were expected to be lifelong conditions or were consistently recurring. Conversely, we categorized diseases as “acute” if they were severe or intense, but resolvable.

We also compiled general Medicaid population and utilization volume for benchmarking. We compared utilization patterns of Medicaid enrollees living with RDs against those without RDs. For this analysis, members were assigned to one of two groups: “acute utilizers” and “chronic utilizers.” Cases were determined to be an acute or chronic disease based on whether they were identified as such by the Chronic Conditions Warehouse’s (CCW) chronic disease algorithm, which categorizes ICD-10 codes by chronicity. The utilization pattern for chronic utilizers was tracked longitudinally, whereas acute utilization patterns were only tracked within one year of the acute disease's first claim record. We looked at services by service type or domain, including inpatient, emergency room (ED), outpatient, primary care, home health, caregiver, LTC, and prescription (Rx) drug utilization.

Results

Population Characteristics

We identified 6,080,890 Medicaid enrollees living with a RD in 2023. Of this total, approximately 3,913,279 million beneficiaries were identified as having a chronic RD, and approximately 2,512,603 million beneficiaries were identified as living with an acute RD. Of the RD population, approximately 38% were White, non-Hispanic; 28% were Hispanic; and approximately 18% were Black, non-Hispanic. Asian, non-Hispanic

comprised just over 4% of enrollees, while Native Americans and Alaska Natives comprised slightly over 1% of members. About 14% of enrollees reported no race/ethnicity. Overall, nearly 60% were women, 40% were men; a small fraction (<0.5%) of enrollee reported no gender.

Table 1. Medicaid Enrollees with a RD, by Race

Demographic Category	# of Rare Disease Enrollees	Rare Disease Proportion
American Indian and Alaska Native (AIAN) non-Hispanic	72,597	1.15%
Asian, non-Hispanic	275,937	4.37%
Black, non-Hispanic	1,128,622	17.86%
Hispanic, all races	1,374,248	21.75%
Multiracial, non-Hispanic	55,176	0.87%
Native Hawaiian and Other Pacific Islander (NHOPI), non-Hispanic	32,461	0.51%
Other, non-Hispanic	90,551	1.43%
White, non-Hispanic	2,379,512	37.66%
Not reported	909,183	14.39%

Table 2. Biological Sex of Medicaid Enrollees with a RD

Biological Sex	# of Enrollees with No Rare Disease Beneficiaries	Rare Disease Proportion
Female	3,737,860	59.16%
Male	2,553,145	40.41%
Not Reported	27,120	0.43%

Age

In 2023, nearly one-quarter of Medicaid members with a RD (23.44%) were 12 years old or younger. Nearly three in 10 (29.2%) enrollees with a RD were younger than age 18. Nearly half of all members with a RD (47.49%) were age 35 or younger. Enrollees ages 36 to 64 with a RD comprised slightly more than one-third of RD Medicaid population (37.67%), whereas beneficiaries ages 65 or older with a RD represented slightly more than 14% of the overall RD population.

Table 3. Medicaid Beneficiaries with a RD, by Age

Age Cohort	# of Beneficiaries with a Rare Disease	% of Medicaid Beneficiaries with a Rare Disease
Ages 0 – 5	1,026,772	16.25%
Ages 6 – 12	468,372	7.41%
Ages 13 – 17	349,775	5.54%
Ages 18 – 21	249,556	3.95%
Ages 22 – 26	273,511	4.33%
Ages 27 – 35	632,706	10.01%

Ages 36 – 49	1,050,866	16.63%
Ages 50 – 64	1,329,554	21.04%
Ages 65+	910,442	14.41%
Not Reported	26,901	0.43%

Service Utilization

Medicaid beneficiaries with a RD utilize significantly more health care services compared to the general beneficiary population, particularly hospital inpatient and emergency services. For inpatient services, we found that all RD members were at least 7.25 times (625%) more likely to have an inpatient visit than non-RD Medicaid enrollees. For ED utilization, individuals with acute RDs and chronic RDs utilized ED services 3.3 times (230%) and 4.7 times (370%), respectively, more than all non-RD enrollees.

When compared with all Medicaid enrollees who utilize LTC services, individuals with chronic RDs were more than 10 times more likely (1,382%) to require these services.

Other differences in utilization between enrollees with RDs and those without were more modest. Individuals with chronic RDs were nearly 6 times (604%) more likely to access outpatient services than all other enrollees. Of the Medicaid members who received primary care services, individuals with chronic RDs were approximately 3.4 times (237%) more likely to seek such services than all non-RD enrollees, respectively. For Table 4, the benchmark is the total Medicaid population.

Table 4. Data on Utilization of Services of Medicaid Beneficiaries with a RD

Services	Visits; In the case of Rx and LTC, Claims	Unique Beneficiaries	Visits (Outpatient Services) Per Beneficiary	Total Count of Beneficiaries Using Services	# of Visits (Services for OP) Per Beneficiary for All Medicaid Beneficiaries	Visits Per 10K Benes (By Utilizer Group)
Inpatient Care Visits						
Acute RD utilizers	2,261,481	970,215	2.33	2,512,603	0.9	9,000.55
Chronic RD Utilizers	3,389,255	1,547,497	2.19	3,913,279	0.87	8,660.91
Benchmark	11,973,756	7,101,103	1.69	96,370,680	0.12	1,242.47
Emergency Care Visits						
Acute RD utilizers	4,387,287	1,240,509	3.54	2,512,603	1.75	17,461.12
Chronic RD Utilizers	9,782,388	3,656,206	2.68	3,913,279	2.5	24,997.93
Benchmark	50,928,413	25,541,778	1.99	96,370,680	0.53	5,284.64
Outpatient Services						

Acute RD Utilizers		1,950,147	11.29	2,512,603	8.76	87,599.52
Chronic RD Utilizers		3,532,464	16.15	3,913,279	14.58	145,751.00
Benchmark		42,070,183	5.52	96,370,680	2.41	24,115.23
Primary Care						
Acute RD Utilizers	8,494,486	910,575	9.33	2,512,603	3.38	3,380.75
Chronic RD Utilizers	21,445,848	3,265,675	6.57	3,913,279	5.48	5,480.28
Benchmark	29,858,505	29,858,505	5.24	96,370,680	1.63	1,625.03
LTC Services						
Acute RD Utilizers	2,181,795	156,233.00	13.97	2,512,603	0.87	868.34
Chronic RD Utilizers	7,205,053	420,873.00	17.12	3,913,279	1.84	1,841.18
Benchmark	11,973,756	7,101,103	1.69	96,370,680	0.12	124.25
Prescription Drugs						
Acute RD Utilizers	62,338,656	1,957,794	31.84	2,512,603	24.81	24,810.39
Chronic RD Utilizers	200,275,281	7,301,205	27.43	3,913,279	51.18	51,178.38
Benchmark	860,365,581	51,608,978	16.67	96,370,680	8.93	8,927.67

Dual Eligibility and Waivers Status

In 2023, of the more than 6 million Medicaid beneficiaries with a RD, nearly one in three (1,936,582 or 30.65%) were dually eligible for Medicare and Medicaid.¹² The proportion of Medicaid beneficiaries with a RD who are dually eligible for Medicare and Medicaid is significantly higher than the proportion of dual-eligible individuals in the total Medicaid population.

Of the more than 6 million Medicaid beneficiaries with RDs in 2023, nearly half (44.71%) qualified for Medicaid through a HCBS waiver, and only 5.26% qualified based on an 1115 waiver.

Table 5. Medicaid Beneficiaries with a RD, by Duals and HCBS Wavier Status

Population Group	# of Beneficiaries with a Rare Disease	Rare Disease Proportion
Non-Dual	4,384,068	69.39%
Dual	1,936,582	30.65%
HCBS Wavier Eligible	2,718,700	44.7%
1115 Waiver Eligible	320,073	5.26%

Geography

We found that approximately one out of every six Medicaid members with a RD (17%) lived in a rural area. Nearly four in 10 Medicaid beneficiaries with a RD (38%) lived in an area that was rural or a rural-suburban mix. We also found that states with higher

population tended to also have higher proportions of Medicaid beneficiaries with a RD (eTable 2 in Supplement).

Table 6. Medicaid Beneficiaries with a RD, by Rurality

Rurality	# of Beneficiaries with a Rare Disease	% of Medicaid Beneficiaries with a Rare Disease
Pure rural	1,080,684	17.7%
Rural-suburban mix	1,280,396	21.0%
Sparse suburban	1,205,942	19.8%
Dense suburban	969,076	15.9%
Urban-suburban mix	854,158	14.0%
Pure urban	710,128	11.6%

Discussion

This analysis provides important new insights regarding Medicaid members with a RD diagnosis. Although many observations could be made from the data and analysis, we highlight a few that may prove the most impactful for policymakers.

First, the data illustrate the disproportionate share of Medicaid beneficiaries with a RD who are children, teens, and young adults. That finding should be of little surprise given that the *European Journal of Human Genetics* reported that approximately 70% of RDs begin in childhood,¹³ and children are a core Medicaid population. In 2023, about 42 million children were enrolled in Medicaid.¹ This finding underscores the degree to which future Medicaid policy changes at the federal or state levels will, in effect, have an outsized impact on care and access dynamics for Medicaid’s youngest members.

Second, the data analysis highlights the reliance that Medicaid enrollees with RDs have on eligibility pathways and services. For example, many individuals qualify for HCBS via a waiver. HCBS is a core component of Medicaid’s LTC offerings, and the data show Medicaid members with a RD use a significantly higher percentage of long-term care services than individuals without a RD (the average RD LTC service rate was 1.26 claims per user and the total was 165.21% higher than the benchmark comparison). Although there is significant state variability with respect to HCBS and LTC program and waiver components, the importance of these services for this population has never been quantifiably demonstrated.

HCBS services are of particular value to many members with RDs, given the significant, ongoing costs associated with providing care, treatment, and support for individuals with RDs. In 2019, the economic burden of RDs (including both direct medical costs and other indirect costs) reached approximately \$1 trillion in the United States.² Of this total, non-medical and uncovered health care costs exceeded \$110 billion.² Such non-medical and non-covered costs included paid daily care, necessary home and vehicle

modifications, and transportation and education costs. This figure also includes health care services not covered by insurance, such as experimental treatments, medical foods, and more.

The significant reliance on HCBS waiver pathways for Medicaid eligibility among individuals with a RD (44.7%) underscores the importance of policy conversations about the continued financing and availability of HCBS benefits.¹⁴

Third, the data provide new insights on the intersection of Medicaid enrollees with RDs and rural health. That nearly four out of 10 beneficiaries with a RD live in areas that are rural or rural-suburban is an important finding, given the long-standing and well-known challenges with accessing comprehensive, timely medical care in rural areas. Federal and state policymakers have long recognized that some of those unique barriers merit specific policy and program approaches. Now that federal and state policymakers are closely following the distribution and use of funds from the Rural Health Transformation Program established in OBBBA, this analysis provides a granular understanding of what proportion of relevant beneficiaries in 2023 were distributed across specific rural geographies.³ Additional granular data analysis of geographic limitations in specialist access and other care services RD beneficiaries require could inform care intervention strategies, access points, and other state and local efforts.

Fourth, this analysis both contributes new insights into health research and implicitly suggests the kinds of research questions that could be answered in future data analyses. For example, a future data analysis could look at 2024 data, examine specific individual rare diseases, scrutinize a subset of type of care interventions and therapeutics, or analyze expenditure-related trends and differences across states for rare diseases.

Fifth, with the enactment and implementation of OBBBA, the next several years will portend an extremely active period of Medicaid policy and program evolution at the federal and state level. Although this analysis has some important methodological limitations, it provides novel and compelling insights not yet well understood or objectively examined at a national level. This analysis may equip a range of audiences with a dispassionate, timely, national overview of important characteristics about Medicaid beneficiaries with RDs and some of their key characteristics relative to the Medicaid program, enabling year-to-year comparisons by state, as many OBBBA implementation specifics will vary by state.

Limitations

The authors acknowledge this analysis has limitations. First, research suggests that perhaps only one or two of every 10 RDs actually has a specific ICD-10 code.¹⁵ Thus, this analysis can be most accurately described as examining characteristics of Medicaid enrollees with a *diagnosed and known* RD. In reality, the number of Americans with Medicaid coverage who have a RD is likely to be higher than reported in the dataset.

Second, claims are used as a proxy for the presence of a RD without any further clinical diagnostic validation, such as cross-referencing claims against patient electronic health record (EHR) data to confirm the diagnosis. By relying only on claims data, we are

unable to discern a differential (i.e., unconfirmed) diagnosis from a confirmed diagnosis.¹⁶

Third, the relationship between a disease concept and a single ICD-10 code is not always one-to-one. This relationship can vary because of overlapping symptoms, varying disease stages, or coding conventions.

Finally, the state of Medicaid data is imperfect and constantly evolving. Most importantly, the COVID-19 public health emergency and Medicaid-related provisions did not expire until spring 2023, and Medicaid enrollment during that period was consequently higher.¹⁷ And additional changes are on the horizon as OBBBA ushers in sweeping and novel changes to state Medicaid programs. Examining the effects of the law on people with RDs and enrolled in Medicaid merits further examination.¹⁸

Conclusion

This national analysis provides new evidence on the characteristics and service utilization of Medicaid enrollees with diagnosed RDs. Using comprehensive Medicaid claims data, the study demonstrates that beneficiaries with RDs account for disproportionately high use of inpatient, emergency, long-term care, and prescription drug services and are more likely to rely on specific eligibility pathways, including dual eligibility and home and community-based services. The findings highlight the central role Medicaid plays in financing and delivering care for people with RDs, particularly children and residents of rural areas. These results establish a foundation for future research and policy evaluation as Medicaid programs continue to evolve.

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